

QUANTERA

Research Funders for Quantum Technologies

Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results of the Programme

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Table of Content

List of abbreviations	3
Disclaimer	3
Copyright notice	3
1. Introduction.....	4
Expected results	4
Communication & dissemination levels	4
2. QuantERA visual identity	5
3. QuantERA ecosystem of stakeholders.....	5
4. Communication & dissemination roadmap	7
Special focus areas.....	9
5. Communication & Dissemination channels	9
6. Showcasing and Monitoring of Funded Projects	11
7. Internal Communication	12
Internal communication main areas.....	12
Internal processes.....	13
8. Summary	14
Appendix 1	16

List of abbreviations

Acronym	Full form
CO	Coordination Office
CS	Call Secretariat
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CSC	Call Steering Committee
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EuroHPC JU	European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking
EuroQCI	European Quantum Communication Infrastructure
F&T	Funding and Tenders
FPA	Framework Partnership Agreement
MB	Management Board
NCN	National Science Centre, Poland
QCB	Quantum Coordination Board
QCN	Quantum Community Network
QSC	QuantERA Steering Committee
QT	Quantum Technologies
QTCG	Quantum Technologies Coordination Group
QUCATS	Quantum Flagship Coordination Action and Support
QuIC	Quantum Industry Consortium
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
PEDR	Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results
R&I	Research and Innovation
RIA	Research and Innovation Action
RRI	Responsible Research & Innovation
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
WP	Work Package

Disclaimer

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1. Introduction

The Plan for the Exploitation and Dissemination of Results (PEDR), developed under the QuantERA III Work Package 5, Task 5.1, describes the Programme's overall approach towards communication and dissemination activities, aimed at increasing visibility and maximising result exploitation in the QT (Quantum Technologies) ecosystem. With various stakeholders playing important role in reaching Programme's objectives, QuantERA focuses on creating and executing clear plan for communication, both internally (within Consortium and Governance bodies) and externally (with researchers, policymakers and a broad range of QT-related actors).

Expected results

QuantERA III activities described in PEDR are focused on maximising Programme's impact through number of targeted actions. With this tailored plan, QuantERA will aim to address its core objectives, i.e.:

- To increase the outreach of the Programme by effective cooperation with various stakeholders from QT community,
- To reinforce visibility and recognition of QuantERA by clearly communicating the beneficial role of the Programme (positioning QuantERA as the place to shape quantum R&I),
- To foster the inclusive R&I community around QT in Europe and beyond by stimulating research connections and strengthening engagement of QuantERA-funded projects in the international community of both academia and industry,
- To enhance the alignment of national, European, and non-European policies in QT,
- To foster dialogue on QuantERA sustainability and support progress towards the continuation of the Programme while ensuring the concrete use and exploitation of the achieved outputs.

Communication & dissemination levels

QuantERA communication & dissemination processes will be conducted at two interdependent levels:

- Programme level – focused on network objectives and activities performed by the QuantERA partners, e.g., efforts on maximising visibility and outreach of QuantERA main task - transnational calls for proposals, ensuring broad access to developed documents and publications, and promoting events organised by or involving QuantERA,
- Project level – targeted at promotion of QuantERA-funded research projects through various activities, including publishing project overviews, involving QuantERA funding recipients to present their work at QuantERA-organised events, and disseminating funded projects results through engagement with other QT-related stakeholders (e.g., the Quantum Flagship).

The overall communication strategy of QuantERA will be built upon use of appropriate tools and channels, applicable for respective activity. By clear identification of the purpose, targeted audience and expected results, QuantERA will continuously increase its visibility in the quantum community and beyond.

2. QuantERA visual identity

Since QuantERA I, the visual identity has been consistently maintained to ensure Programme's recognition and coherence among partners and stakeholders. With the launch of QuantERA III, ensuring the accuracy and consistency of the presented information became a priority. As initial part of this effort, specific updates to the logo were implemented - the text beneath "QuantERA" was revised from "ERA-Net Cofund" to "Research Funders for Quantum Technologies." This modification explicitly reflects the transition of the Programme from an ERA-NET Cofund under Horizon 2020 to a Research and Innovation Action (RIA) within Horizon Europe, aligning the visual identity with the Programme's current funding mechanism and objectives. All other visual elements have remained unchanged, and the original colour scheme continues to be used.

To ensure clarity and ease of use, a logo pack has been made available on the QuantERA website under the ["Media"](#) section. It includes different versions of the logo (short version, version with the tagline, and the emblem) in multiple formats and can be used by Consortium partners and Programme beneficiaries to ensure consistent and professional presentation across all dissemination materials.

Throughout QuantERA III, further efforts will focus on maintaining a coherent visual identity and ensuring partners have access to the tools needed for consistent communication. Particular attention will be paid to the continuous refinement of visual identity elements, with the aim of improving accessibility, clarity, and recognisability, while ensuring overall coherence across all communication and dissemination tools.

3. QuantERA ecosystem of stakeholders

Operating in the field of QT, QuantERA engages in diverse activities with various stakeholder groups. With identification of those broad target audiences QuantERA maps key activities and channels used for enhancing those collaborations.

QuantERA stakeholder map (as presented in [FIGURE 1](#)), shows multiplicity of actors and relationships between them. Within QuantERA network itself, robust internal collaboration exists between **QuantERA Coordinator (NCN)**, **Research Funding Organisations (RFOs)** participating in the Programme, and **Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)** providing guidance on research directions. Based on this foundation for Programme's operation, QuantERA further defines its strategy of collaboration with **other actors**:

- **RFOs outside the QuantERA Consortium** – to further expand the network through systematic identification of new potential partnerships, focused on bringing added value for the Programme,
- **European Commission** – to efficiently deliver the expected results from the Programme, as well as to collaborate for building strong quantum community within Europe,
- **Quantum Flagship**, as a key EC research and innovation initiative for QT development and for strengthening Europe's position in global QT landscape – to ensure alignment of activities, including collaboration with bodies such as QCN (Quantum Community Network), QCB (Quantum Coordination Board), supportive CSA (QUCATS and the follow-ups), etc.

- **QT-related initiatives and actors** – to continuously identify areas for enhancing synergies within the European quantum landscape; targeted at QTCG (Quantum Technologies Coordination Group), Quantum Framework Partnership Agreements (FPA), EuroHPC JU, EuroQCI and others,
- **QuantERA research projects** (applicants and beneficiaries of QuantERA-funded calls) – to advance European QT capacity through transnational collaborations,
- **Academia** – to build links within the QT research community, and to cooperate with renowned scientists in the evaluation process of transnational calls,
- **Business & Industry** (including QuIC - European Quantum Industry Consortium) – to expand QuantERA transnational calls outreach, enabling progression pathways from ideas to applications,
- **Media** – to increase visibility, recognition and understanding of QuantERA through clear and accessible communication,
- **General Public** – to raise awareness of QT importance and benefits of its wide spectrum of applications.

FIGURE 1. QUANTERA STAKEHOLDER MAP

For each of the identified stakeholder groups, tailored approach with specific language and suitable communication channels will be applied (as described in [TABLE 2](#)).

4. Communication & dissemination roadmap

The QuantERA III PEDR reflects the Programme's objectives and outlined tasks. **TABLE 1** presents the key areas addressed within the QuantERA III Work Plan, each accompanied by its corresponding communication and dissemination purposes, the tools used to achieve them, and the target stakeholders. This structured approach ensures that all dissemination activities effectively contribute to maximising the impact of the Programme's outcomes.

TABLE 2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION FOR WORK PLAN AREAS

Work plan area	Purposes	Tools & formats	Targeted stakeholders	WP
Joint programming under HE RIA with a cascading grant mechanism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Increasing understanding and knowledge about the QuantERA Programme and QT ✓ Increasing synergy in efforts in Europe and beyond ✓ Ensuring visibility of QuantERA Programme and its activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Publications ✓ Presentations ✓ Newsletter ✓ Short videos ✓ Infographics/visualisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ RFOs ✓ SAB ✓ EC ✓ Quantum Flagship ✓ QT-related initiatives ✓ QuantERA projects ✓ General public ✓ Media 	1, 5, 6
Calls for Transnational Projects in QT – launch and outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Increasing knowledge and understanding of the call topics and requirements ✓ Community building around the call topics and liaising with other stakeholders ✓ Fostering broad transnational collaboration ✓ Increasing visibility of the Programme and funded research 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Call Communication Toolkit: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - leaflet - press release ✓ Call statistics ✓ Call webinars ✓ Call webpage ✓ List of funded projects ✓ Newsletter ✓ Partner Search Tool 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ RFOs ✓ EC ✓ QuantERA projects ✓ Academia ✓ Business & Industry ✓ General public ✓ Media 	2, 3, 5
Funded Projects monitoring and achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Enhancing visibility of the funded projects ✓ Increasing knowledge and understanding of QT ✓ Raising awareness among the general public of the potential societal impacts of QT ✓ Incentive for setting up various forms of new collaborations, including industry ✓ Monitoring progress of the funded projects ✓ Facilitating the exploitation of project research results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Funded projects catalogue ✓ Individual projects' webpages ✓ Newsletter ✓ Infographics/visualisations ✓ Project Search Tool ✓ Project posters ✓ Project presentations ✓ Project publications 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ RFOs ✓ SAB ✓ EC ✓ Quantum Flagship ✓ QT-related initiatives ✓ QuantERA projects ✓ Academia ✓ Business & Industry ✓ General public ✓ Media 	3, 4, 5
Mapping Public Policies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Raising awareness on developments of public policies and funding instruments in QT ✓ Enabling identification of EU-wide directions ✓ Sharing and advocating good practices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Report ✓ Mapping webpage ✓ Presentations ✓ Newsletter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ RFOs ✓ EC ✓ Quantum Flagship ✓ QT-related initiatives ✓ QuantERA projects ✓ Academia ✓ Business & Industry ✓ General public ✓ Media 	6, 5

Work plan area	Purposes	Tools & formats	Targeted stakeholders	WP
Impact Assessment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Providing valuable insights into the Programme's effectiveness, relevance, and efficiency ✓ Enabling identification of directions for future QuantERA development and future EU programming 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Reports ✓ Impact webpage ✓ Presentations ✓ Newsletter ✓ Short videos ✓ Infographics/visualisations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ RFOs ✓ SAB ✓ EC ✓ Quantum Flagship ✓ QT-related initiatives ✓ QuantERA projects ✓ Academia ✓ Business & Industry ✓ General public ✓ Media 	4, 5
Sustainability Strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Providing a vision for the future of the Programme ✓ Raising awareness among stakeholders about the importance of ensuring Programme's long-term sustainability ✓ Establishing forum for discussion on the future of QT funding and QuantERA sustainability in the context of future EU programming ✓ Facilitating stakeholders' commitment to maintaining and expanding the Programme's activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Sustainability Strategy ✓ Policy recommendations ✓ Newsletter ✓ Panel discussions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ RFOs ✓ SAB ✓ EC ✓ Quantum Flagship ✓ QT-related initiatives 	4, 5
Striving towards Inclusivity and Gender Balance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Promoting diversity and inclusiveness in quantum R&I ✓ Engaging in ongoing dialogue on various aspects of inclusiveness with multiple stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Reports ✓ Presentations ✓ Guidelines ✓ Newsletter ✓ Workshops ✓ Panel discussions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ RFOs ✓ EC ✓ Quantum Flagship ✓ QT-related initiatives ✓ QuantERA projects ✓ Academia ✓ Business & Industry ✓ General public ✓ Media 	5
Opening for International Cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Defining win-win international collaborations for QuantERA network and the R&I ✓ Raising awareness of global collaboration opportunities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Presentations ✓ Roadmap for International Collaboration ✓ Webinars about QuantERA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ RFOs ✓ SAB ✓ EC ✓ Quantum Flagship ✓ QT-related initiatives ✓ QuantERA projects 	6, 5
Liaison with Stakeholders in QT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Fostering dialogue and links with stakeholders in QT ✓ Facilitation of synergies between QuantERA projects and the Quantum Flagship ✓ Fostering closer collaboration with other regions of the world 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Presentations ✓ Newsletter ✓ Webinars ✓ Workshops ✓ Panel discussions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ RFOs ✓ EC ✓ Quantum Flagship ✓ QT-related initiatives ✓ QuantERA projects ✓ Academia ✓ Business & Industry 	5, 6

Special focus areas

Within all communication and dissemination activities QuantERA III will put special emphasis on the following aspects:

Promoting diversity and inclusiveness

One of the key aspects of QuantERA Programme remains to be promotion of gender balance and participation of researchers from Widening countries. In both areas QuantERA will consequently emphasise the importance on building diverse and inclusive quantum community. Blueprint for those activities is set by a document prepared under QuantERA II: [Revised “QuantERA RRI guidelines for research community” with a focus on gender equality in research community](#). As an update of ‘[Responsible Research and Innovation Guidelines](#)’ published in 2018 under QuantERA I, the new document provides a thorough overview of key dimensions to be considered while fostering inclusive and open research culture.

Building upon guidelines set by previous editions QuantERA III will continue actions focused on increased inclusiveness and broadening participation of Widening countries.

Principal actions will be implemented through transnational calls for proposals, as well as through QuantERA events, including a panel session on diversity and inclusiveness envisioned as one of QuantERA III implementation milestones.

Application of Open Science principles

Recognising the importance of unrestricted access to data and research results, QuantERA will actively promote Open Science mindset among its Consortium Members and beneficiaries of transnational calls. To ensure proper understanding and adherence to those rules, as part of deliverable D1.2 - Data Management Plan (DMP) for QuantERA III, short guides will be shared with two groups:

- **One-pager for QuantERA Consortium** – all key information from DMP, divided into main categories applicable for Programme partners, with useful guidance on licenses and repositories,
- **Guidelines for funded projects** – main requirements, good practices and references to additional materials concerning full scope of data management in research projects.

The concise and graphic format in both cases was chosen as part of overall QuantERA communication strategy which aims at delivering the most important information in a clear and user-friendly format. Additional guidance will be shared in reply to emerging needs, as QuantERA Programme continues to monitor official requirements and international standards in data management, which will be included in the deliverable D1.8 – Revised Data Management Plan.

5. Communication & Dissemination channels

To maximise the dissemination and visibility of its results, as well as to support internal collaboration QuantERA III will employ a combination of communication channels. These means will also play a key role in raising awareness of Programme activities and encouraging active engagement among relevant stakeholder groups.

The QuantERA website (<https://quantera.eu/>), developed at the inception of the Programme and continuously updated, will continue serving as the primary Programme platform fulfilling following functions:

- Knowledge services, providing resources such as factsheets, briefing papers, visualisations, and reports,
- Communication services, engaging the general audience with updates on QuantERA’s activities and their outcomes through the “News” section as well as the QuantERA’s newsletter (which currently reaches almost 1000 subscribers),
- Collaboration services, offering a dedicated “Partner Area”, designed as a shared space for the QuantERA Consortium to cooperate and share files.

FIGURE 2 below illustrates the principal set of QuantERA channels that will underpin the Programme’s website and guide the implementation of QuantERA communication approach.

FIGURE 2. OVERVIEW OF QUANTERA DISSEMINATION CHANNELS

The selection and use of relevant channels will be tailored to the specific messages being conveyed, the communication objectives pursued, and the particular stakeholder groups targeted.

For the purposes of interaction and collaboration among stakeholders, QuantERA III will also employ a range of dedicated digital instruments. Platforms such as Microsoft Teams, Cisco Webex, and ClickMeeting will be used to support online meetings, webinars, workshops, and structured exchanges. To further enhance interactions during events, supplementary applications, such as

Miro and Mentimeter, may be used to facilitate collaborative exercises, real-time input, and increased participant involvement.

In addition to QuantERA's own communication tools, external platforms will play an important role in amplifying outreach. This includes:

- The websites and media of RFOs within the QuantERA III Consortium,
- QT-related and supportive initiatives, e.g., the Quantum Flagship,
- EU-level platforms, especially relevant in the context of QuantERA call announcements.

All these channels will be used will be used to enhance visibility and ensure broad dissemination across the European research community.

6. Showcasing and Monitoring of Funded Projects

At the core of the QuantERA Programme are its funded research projects which represent the main instrument for achieving the Programme's objectives and advancing QT. Recognising their central role, QuantERA ensures that these projects are effectively promoted, clearly presented, and continuously monitored. Within QuantERA III, these efforts are being further strengthened and systematised to maximise the impact and visibility of project results.

Key dissemination and monitoring actions will include:

- Presentation and evaluation during QuantERA events: Funded projects will be regularly showcased through poster sessions and presentations during QuantERA III conferences, with an emphasis on active participation and structured feedback collection. Projects will be encouraged to actively use QuantERA events to highlight progress and outcomes, fostering interaction and knowledge exchange with other stakeholders.
- Online visibility and Project Search Tool: As practiced within previous editions of QuantERA, each funded project will have a dedicated webpage on the Programme's website containing essential information such as the abstract, consortium composition, and funding agencies involved. These pages will be integrated into the existing database and will be accessible through the *Project Search Tool* which serves as a central database of funded projects. New webpages will ensure comprehensive and up-to-date coverage of the Programme's portfolio.
- Project catalogues: For each QuantERA III call, a project catalogue summarising the key data and outcomes of funded projects will be prepared and disseminated via the website and social media. These publications will highlight QuantERA's contribution to the QT landscape.
- Monitoring and exploitation of funded projects results: The Programme plans to regularly showcase projects achievements, success stories and promote periodic reports through QuantERA communication channels. These measures will ensure that project outcomes are effectively disseminated, foster collaboration, and increase the Programme's visibility across the European and international quantum research community.

The QuantERA website (www.quantera.eu) and social media channels (LinkedIn, Facebook, and X) will be continuously monitored as part of QuantERA III to evaluate the effectiveness of communication and dissemination efforts, as well as to introduce relevant modifications based on insights derived from this analysis. An example of such data-driven adjustments can be seen in the actions taken during the launch phase of QuantERA III, when the website underwent a structural

and visual modernisation to improve navigation, accessibility, and visibility. Website analytics consistently have shown that project-related pages attract the highest number of visits. In response, a direct “Funded Projects” button was introduced on the homepage to facilitate access. In addition, the Consortium section was redesigned, introducing a new navigation feature that allows users to switch between previous QuantERA editions and the current partner composition. These changes enhance transparency and facilitate contact among stakeholders. Further improvements are planned to ensure that the website remains a dynamic and user-oriented platform for project communication, including the integration of audiovisual materials which allow for easier presentation of QuantERA activities, key data, findings, and project achievements.

In parallel, QuantERA III will continue to use social media to maximise Programme’s visibility and communicate project results. QuantERA’s social media presence continues to grow. As of November 2025, the Programme reaches 1,115 followers on LinkedIn, 1,768 on X, and around 1,000 on Facebook, confirming steady engagement across platforms. Building on the foundations established in earlier editions, regular updates will be maintained, and further efforts will focus on increasing outreach and engagement, including the use of more diverse and user-friendly content formats such as audiovisual materials.

7. Internal Communication

As one of Europe’s largest networks dedicated to QT and given its strong focus on external communication and dissemination, QuantERA also recognises the pivotal role of its internal communication. With 40 RFOs from 30 countries in QuantERA III, ensuring clear and effective communication within the Consortium is one of Coordinator’s key tasks.

Internal communication main areas

Main focus of QuantERA III Programme’s internal communication will span three areas:

1. **Communication from Coordinator and among Consortium partners** – focused on appropriate flow of information among all members of QuantERA III Consortium, as well as targeted communication with respective partners,
2. **Communication between QuantERA Governance Bodies** (incl. SAB, QCS, CSC, CS) - assuring engagement and timely execution of processes linked with main QuantERA activities,
3. **Communication between QuantERA and EC** – continuous collaboration and updates, including reports, deliverables and messages shared via F&T Portal.

QuantERA developed dedicated tools to facilitate internal collaboration, yet it will also use its external communication channels (e.g., website, newsletter) to enhance the internal flow of information. Additionally, dedicated SharePoint will serve as a secure workspace for internal collaboration, offering different levels of access to materials and requiring registration, which enables effective tracking of participation and engagement. Details and key aspects of their application are presented in [TABLE 3](#).

TABLE 3. OVERVIEW OF QUANTERA INTERNAL COMMUNICATION.

Targeted Group	Means of communication (channels)	Key focus
Call Secretariat (CS)	'QuantERA Calls' Share Point site Email correspondence Meetings	Smooth execution of all call-related tasks, including process of calls' announcement, evaluation and results
Call Steering Committee (CSC)	QuantERA website (including Partner Area) Email correspondence QuantERA events & meetings	Smooth cooperation on calls execution and maximisation of impact from funded research projects
Consortium Members/ QuantERA Steering Committee (QSC)	QuantERA website (including Partner Area) Email correspondence QuantERA events & meetings	Close cooperation in achieving overall QuantERA Programme objectives, Effective flow of information on key QuantERA topics
European Commission (EC)	Funding & Tenders Portal Email correspondence QuantERA events & meetings	Continuous reporting of Programme's progress, Effective information exchange with EC representatives
Management Board (MB)	Email correspondence Meetings	Enhancing collaboration on Programme tasks and deliverables, Clear view on progress and possible risks
Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)	QuantERA website Email correspondence QuantERA events & meetings	Support in defining scientific scope of calls, outreach for new collaborations, QuantERA new directions and the Programme's promotion

QuantERA III will use combination of traditional and modern communication tools to ensure optimal flow of information among all listed groups. Approach described in the table above will be subject to continuous improvement, with necessary adjustments to used solutions and frequency of communication activities, as needed.

Internal processes

QuantERA Programme operates within a highly complex environment, characterised by numerous interdependent activities. To maintain its operational success, QuantERA follows the general blueprint for its recurrent processes, with necessary adaptive approach. The high-level overview of their execution, developed over the course of almost 10 years of QuantERA, is presented in **FIGURE 3**.

FIGURE 3. KEY RECURRING STEPS IN QUANTERA PROCESSES.

In each case, action is initiated by Coordinator to grant alignment with overall Programme's objectives and direction. Clear definition of contributors and plan of activities facilitates proper

engagement and delivery of expected results. Regardless of specific topic/ area, each process is always concluded with reflection on possible improvements in the future.

Among many processes conducted within QuantERA there are a few particularly important that require close collaboration within the Consortium and have high impact on overall Programme, namely:

- Document development,
- Event organisation,
- Preparing and launching transnational calls.

With a special focus put on their delivery, a more detailed mapping was prepared, with clear indication of necessary sequence of steps. While key information is listed in **TABLE 4**, the full workflows are part of **APPENDIX 1**.

TABLE 4. MAIN QUANTERA INTERNAL PROCESSES

Process	Document development	Event organisation	Call launch
Inputs	Definition and objectives included in QuantERA Grant Agreement	Key focus derived from QuantERA Grant Agreement, facilitated by Consortium discussions	General framework set by QuantERA key documents (Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement) and SAB recommendations
Scope	Development of QuantERA reports (incl. official QuantERA Programme deliverables)	Full preparation plan of organisation of QuantERA events	Planning and launching transnational calls for proposals
Participants	Task Leader and Task Contributors in close collaboration with Coordinator	The hosting Organisation in close collaboration with Coordinator	Coordinator, Call Secretariat and Call Steering Committee, Strategic Advisory Board
Outputs	Official QuantERA document (report, guideline or other)	Event as a valuable discussions and networking forum within quantum community	Call Announcement with requirements and evaluation description

Benefitting from experience gained from previous editions, QuantERA III will continue to work on the most efficient internal collaboration approach which will facilitate achievement of overall Programme’s objectives.

8. Summary

With this deliverable QuantERA III defines its overall strategy towards effective communication, dissemination and exploitation of Programme’s results through:

- Defining key areas of focus and main stakeholder’s groups to be targeted,
- Systematic approach towards activities, tools and channels used,
- Continuous monitoring of implemented actions efficiency,
- Defining key internal communication aspects.

QuantERA III will implement a structured, multi-level communication model that supports both Programme-level outreach and the promotion of funded research projects. Particular emphasis will

be placed on maintaining a coherent visual identity, promoting project achievements, fostering inclusiveness and gender balance, supporting open science practices, and strengthening connections within the European and international quantum technologies landscape.

QuantERA activities, targeted at increase of Programme's visibility, will also act as a prerequisite for stimulating new collaborations and further consolidation of quantum community. To reach its objectives and maximise impact, QuantERA will develop relevant materials, continuously expand its presence in traditional and social media, and will either organise or actively take part in a range of quantum-related events.

Considering rapid changes in quantum environment, this plan will be a subject of continuous adjustments, to meet emerging needs and assure most effective approach towards communication and dissemination activities.

Appendix 1

QuantERA documents development

Colour code:

Formal steps

Discussions/
meetings

Documents

Final step/
completion of task

QuantERA event organisation

Colour code:	 Formal steps	 Discussions/ meetings	 Actions	 Final step/ completion of task
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QuantERA Calls

Colour code: Formal steps Discussions/ meetings Actions Final step/ completion of task